

LIMOGES PORCELAIN

GESTURE SEGMENTATION :

II. JOINING THE HANDLE

GX010025 Video excerpt (Egocentric camera) (Practitioner 2) 5'38

GX010063 Video excerpt (Frontal camera) (Practitioner 25'18

[On the worktable, a wooden board with the bodies of two cups and 4 handles. There is also a cutter, a pot with porcelain “glue” (slip + 4 or 5 drops of vinegar), two sponges and a basin filled with water].

Technical note: the joining or fitting operation should be done when the parts (body and handles in this case) have acquired the texture known as ‘leather hard stage’ (“texture cuir”)

Posture: She is sitting, at a slight angle to the work table. The back is straight and the chin slightly tucked in.

1. CUTTING OFF THE HANDLE ENDS

0'10'' - 0'21'' She takes a handle with her left hand and with her right hand, using a cutter, she removes the irregularities from both ends of the handle in order to smooth these surfaces.

0'21" - 0'56" She repeats the operation with the other three handles.

2. ATTACHING THE HANDLES

2.1. POSITIONING + FIXING OF HANDLE #1 (Porcelain glue):

2.1.1. Dipping in the handle in porcelain “glue” (slip + few drops of vinegar).

0'59'' - 1'06'' She takes and dips first one end of the handle and then the other in the glue.

2.1.2. Positioning the handle (perpendicular to the cup base)

To place the handle and carry out this first fixing stage, the cup is turned over in several positions and alternately placed on the board or held in the air in the hands.

2.1.3. Sticking the handle to the body of the cup.

1'06''- 1'26'' She places and fixes the handle, from top to bottom, on the side of the body of the cup, exerting several points of controlled pressure, and varying these points on the outside and inside of the cup, on the junction areas. Pressure is applied by pinching with the thumb and forefinger.

2.1.4. Moistening the handle area (with sponge)

1'29''- 1'33'' She takes a sponge and soaks it in the water in the basin. Rubbing gently with the sponge, she moistens the side of the cup opposite the handle she has just attach

1'33''- 2'04'' She takes a second handle and attaches it to the cup.

When she exerts pressure with her fingers on the junction points between the body of the cup and the handle on the outside, she counterbalances this pressure by pressing with the other hand on the inside of the cup and in the opposite direction to the pressure exerted from the outside. The gestures used to fix the handles are a dynamic interplay of pressure and counter-pressure exerted simultaneously to avoid breaking the still fragile piece (unfired and still slightly wet, leather hard stage).

2.2. ATTACHING THE HANDLE #2 (SOLID TOOL: Wooden modelling tool)

2'10" - 2'22" She takes a small, thin wooden stick with a pointed tip and dips it into the slip and then into the water. With this tool, she irons out the junction points between the body of the cup and the handle.

2.3. ATTACHING THE HANDLE #3 (SOFT TOOL: Brush)

2'23'' - 3'19 She dips a brush in water and then in glue, ironing and smoothing the junction points, alternating between glue and water, to fill the gap between the body of the cup and the handle. She washes the excess water from the brush onto the sponge. This operation also serves to mop up the water that runs down her forearm every time she takes water from the basin.

Several operations:

2.3.1. Wet the brush.

2.3.2. Discharge excess water onto a workpiece.

2.3.3. Take some glue with the brush.

2.3.4. Filling the joints (between the handle and the body of the cup) with slip

2.3.5. Smoothing the joints with the brush.

She only looks at the brush as she dips it into the water in the basin

Dipping brush in water

Discharge excess water from the brush onto the sponge

Taking glue with the brush

Filling the joints with slip

Smoothing the joints with the brush.

3'39'' - 5'23'' She repeats these following operations with the second cup:

- Using the fingers, place and fix the first handle with glue.

- Using the fingers, place and fix the second handle with glue.

- Filling and smoothing the gap between the body of the cup and the handle (the 4 points of contact) with the brush dipped in water and glue, turning the cup in your hand.

5'23" Gently, she places the cup on the board.

